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EDITORIAL DESK

I wish to express my profound gratitude to Almighty God for the grace to successfully complete the volume 2 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP).

The twelve articles were the products of well researched papers that were presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe. These published articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP

Head, Editorial Team

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TECHNOSTRESS MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AND LECTURERS' PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper delves into technostress management strategies and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The challenges contributing to technostress management among lecturers hinged on heavy workloads, lack of technological skills and constant changes in technology. The study adopted a correlational design. The population of the study comprised 3,301 academic staff in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The sample size was 360 lecturers selected through simple random sampling techniques from four public universities. Two research questions were asked and two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. Two research instruments titled 'Technostress Management Strategies Questionnaire' (TMSQ) and the 'Lecturers Productivity Questionnaire' (LPQ) were used for data collection. The validity of the instruments was tested by an expert and the reliability consistency of the instruments was 0.62 and 0.64 using Cronbach's alpha. The data collected were analysed using inferential statistical analysis. Pearson Product Moment correlation was used to analyse hypotheses via Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0. The findings of hypotheses 1 and 2 showed that a significant relationship existed between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = .594$; $N=360$; $p<0.05$); and a significant relationship existed between technostress strategic planning and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria ($r = .621$; $N=360$; $p<0.05$). Based on the findings, the study concluded that strategic planning and a conducive work environment would enhance lecturers to manage technostress. Therefore, it is recommended amongst others that university management and policymakers should design strategic planning and develop monitoring system strategies to support lecturers in managing technostress and ultimately improving their productivity.

Keywords: Lecturer, Management, Productivity, Strategies and Technostress

INTRODUCTION

Globally, tertiary education is also known as the third level of education which takes place after secondary school and offers academic degrees, diplomas, and certificates for students. According to Shittu, Ajimuse and Idowu (2020), tertiary education is given after secondary education in universities, colleges of education, polytechnics, and mono technic including those institutions offering correspondence courses. Among all the tertiary institutions, the university is the ivory tower and a citadel of learning where teaching, research and community service are core values and designed to provide advanced knowledge and skills in socio-economic and technology. However, the rapid technological advancement has brought about a parallel challenge to academia known as technostress. Technostress appears to be a state of physical, mental and emotional fatigue caused by the excessive use of technology by individuals in their workplace or professional lives. In the university context, it is a form of academic stress that arises from the inability to cope with the demands of technology leading to feelings of anxiety, frustration and burnout related to the use of technology for teaching, research, and community service. However, some common causes of

technostress include information overload; cyberbullying and online harassment; pressure to constantly update skills and knowledge; poor user experience and interface design, and fear of technology replacing human jobs.

Moreover, the university system uses technology extensively to automate academic processes and enhance the teaching and learning process without stress. According to Wang et al (2018), technology is being used for academic administration and student self-service, through applications such as student life cycle management, learning management systems, attendance management system and online learning that reduce higher education costs for students and give positive perception towards integrating ICT in the classroom. Perhaps, the use of technology among academic staff in Nigerian public universities seems to be become worrisome and crucial due to technostress management. Technostress is characterized by the "inability to cope with new technologies," To manage technostress in public universities, lecturers can take the following steps: encouraging open communication and support; implementing technology-related policies and training; taking regular breaks and practising self-care; setting boundaries for technological use; and fostering a healthy work-life balance. Therefore, this study seeks to address this critical gap in knowledge by conducting comprehensive research on the relationship between technostress and academic staff productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. By identifying the specific stressors associated with technology use and developing effective strategies for mitigating technostress. Productivity is a measure of how well resources such as information, finance, human and physical resources are combined and utilized to accomplish specific and desirable results (Ejiogu in Abdulganiyu, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

Technology has become an important pillar of 21st-century careers and some lecturers in Nigerian public universities are bedevilled with chronic technological stress. Technostress has posed challenges to some university lecturers and affected their academic productivity due to a lack of monitoring systems and strategic planning. The symptoms of technostress in academia include headaches and eye strain; fatigue and decreased productivity; irritability and mood swings; sleep disturbances; and decreased job satisfaction. However, some of these challenges culminated in to lack of digital literacy; insufficient support and internet facilities; information overload; lecturers' resistance to change and adopt new technology innovation; lack of institutional support on academic staff training and development; online security, data privacy and cyberbullying; time management; digital divide and unequal access to technology; well-being and mental health of lecturers in Nigerian public universities. Therefore, the extent of lecturers' efficiency and effectiveness in teaching, research and community service responsibility may not be guaranteed in the face of technostress challenges and culminated in low productivity. The frequency of technostress among public university lecturers in Nigeria needs urgent attention because the current generation of lecturers are fascinating group to research due to their unique traits to perform their academic tasks.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to:

1. Examine the relationship between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.
2. Determine the relationship between technostress strategic planning and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were raised:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between technostress strategic planning and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study anchored on Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress and Coping. In the 1950s and 1960s, Lazarus laid the groundwork for the transactional model of stress and coping, which he initially detailed in his book *Psychological Stress and the Coping Process*, published in 1966. Building upon extensive research in collaboration with Susan Folkman during the 1970s and 1980s, they further refined and elucidated this model in their book *Stress, Appraisal, and Coping* (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984). This model underscores that stress arises from an individual's evaluation of a situation and their perceived capacity to manage it. It posits that stress occurs when an individual views a situation as surpassing their available resources or their ability to cope. The conceptual framework for this study is based on the Technostress Framework proposed by Tarafdar, Cooper and Stich (2017). This framework identifies four primary sources of technostress in organizational contexts: Techno-overload, Techno-invasion, Techno-complexity, and Techno-uncertainty. These sources of technostress can lead to adverse outcomes such as reduced job satisfaction, decreased productivity, and increased turnover intentions.

Fig. 1 Research model

In the context of technostress, this framework suggests that academic staff members will experience technostress when they perceive the demands and complexities of technology use as overwhelming and beyond their coping capabilities. Technostress is a universal phenomenon that every human being experiences in life regardless of age, gender, occupation or socio-economic status. Perhaps, in 1984, technostress was widely known as a pandemic disease caused by an individual's inability to adapt to the uses of technology. The term "Technostress" was coined by American psychologist Craig Brod in his 1984 book "Technostress: The Human Cost of the Computer Revolution," published by Addison Wesley. Brod was the first to identify the stress associated with the use of technology and its impact on psychological well-being. Technostress is a type of stress caused by the negative impact of technology on users which includes feelings of frustration, anxiety and burnout. According to Narahari and Koneru (2017), technostress is defined as a disease of adaptation caused by an

inability to cope with new technologies healthily. Besides, the use of information communication technology enables public universities in Nigeria to streamline academic administration, bring transparency, and speed up academic data processing. Integrating technology in the classroom is believed to improve the teaching and learning process (Mirzajani et al., 2016). The integration of technology in higher education has been instrumental in enhancing teaching, research, and administrative processes in universities worldwide. The utilization of technology-enhanced learning (TEL) has experienced a sharp surge in academia, driven by government incentives and the need to meet the expectations of students (Dunn and Kennedy, 2019). Within academic institutions, technology is harnessed for tasks related to academic administration and student self-service, facilitated by applications like student life cycle management, Learning Management Systems, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), and integrated digital-based assessment (Barana et al., 2016).

In the digital age, university lecturers use technology to perform their obligations in teaching, research, and community services. Technology aids lecturers in lectures delivering, students' seminars, practical demonstrations, preparing for students' classes, teaching practice exercises; invigilation of students' examinations; marking and grading of examination scripts and holding trust for the implemented curriculum of higher education. The excess workload of lecturers encumbers many administrative assignments like Head of Department, Dean, Director, and Vice-Chancellor positions. However, technology helps the academic staff of the university to facilitate research on academic publications and assessment of lecturers' promotion, attend national and international academic conferences, and supervise undergraduate projects and postgraduate dissertations and PhD theses. This is especially true for university teachers where there is a proverb well-circulated: "publish or perish". A lecturer must publish a good number of articles in referred journals with a good reputation; he/she should attend national and international seminars, conferences, workshops, and training programs to gather and develop up-to-date knowledge and information about teaching, learning and development (Mahmood and Yaqub in Shittu, Yekinni & Adedapo, 2022). The certified lecturer possesses a bachelor's degree; master's and most importantly PhD. Therefore, the use of technology reduces stress and workload for lecturers in public universities to be more productive while the fear of the use of technology causes technostress and low productivity. Lecturer productivity seems to be the efficiency and effectiveness of a lecturer in performing their goals and responsibilities. It encompasses teaching and delivering high-quality lectures; conducting innovative research and publishing papers for contribution to knowledge; rendering professional service activities to the community; curriculum development and updating programs to reflect best practices and industry needs; providing mentorship for junior colleagues and students for attainment of academic excellence; supervision of student projects, dissertation and theses at the appropriate time.

In addition, university lecturers are particularly vulnerable to technostress due to the increasing demands of digital teaching, online resources and administrative bottlenecks. The excess workload for lecturers in public universities in Lagos State increases at geometric progression; while the lecturers' is at arithmetic progression which is the major cause of stress (Shittu, Yekinni & Adedapo, 2022). Effective technostress management strategies such as digital literacy training; seeking support from colleagues and the ICT department; regular breaks and self-care; fostering a growth mindset towards technology, engaging in regular technology detox and digital decluttering; developing coping strategies for technology-related frustrations; encouraging open communication and feedback and embracing flexible and adaptable technology use can help lecturers in Nigerian public university to be more

productive in teaching, research and community service. Technostress management seems to be a systematic process of planning, organising, controlling, monitoring and reporting an attitude of people toward the uses of technology in performing a task. Lecturers are bedevilled with academic stress due to excess workload in the teaching occupation. According to Adeshina (2021), stress is the feeling of pressure or worry when there is a problem or issue going on in a person's life; it's emotional or physical tension as the thought of the problems at hand makes one nervous, agitated, or frustrated. If stress is allowed to become excessive, it may lead to sickness or psychosomatic disorders like fever, sneezing, hypertension, peptic ulcers, colitis, high blood pressure, constipation, alcoholism, insomnia, chronic fatigue, migraine, heart disease, dizziness, and nervous dermatitis. Adeshina (2021) posited that physical symptoms of stress include low energy, headaches (migraine most likely), chest pain or rapid heartbeat, stomach upset, high blood pressure, difficulty in breathing, insomnia, and frequent colds among others. All these symptoms lead to low productivity among lecturers in public universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study research design was correlational. The target population comprised all 3,301 lecturers from the University of Lagos (UNILAG); Lagos State University (LASU); Lagos State University of Education (LASUED); and Lagos State University of Science and Technology (LASUSTECH). The sample size comprised 360 lecturers randomly selected through a simple random sampling technique. Two null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance and research instruments titled 'Technostress Management Strategies Questionnaire' (TMSQ) and 'Lecturers Productivity Questionnaire' (LPQ) were used for data collection. The questionnaire is divided into two sections: Section A and B. Section A contains the personal information of the respondents and section B contains the 20 items structured around the research questions. Each statement is measured on a four-point modifier Likert-type-rating scale, namely: "Strongly Agree (SA)", "Agree (A)", "Strongly Disagree (SD)" and "Disagree (D)". The questionnaire was purposively administered to 360 lecturers selected from the Faculty of Social Sciences, Faculty of Education, Faculty of Law, Faculty of Art, Faculty of Science, Faculty of Engineering, and Faculty of Management Science in four universities under study. 40 academic staff were randomly selected from each of the faculties selected for the study. The validity of the instruments was ensured by test experts and subjected to content validity and the reliability index of the instrument was persistently determined through Cronbach's alpha at 0.62 and 0.64 meaning that the instrument is reliable. The data collected were analysed using inferential statistical analysis. Pearson Product Moment correlation was used to analyse hypotheses 1 and 2 through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Pearson’s correlation analysis between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

		Correlations	
Variables		Technostress Monitoring Systems	Lecturers’ Productivity
Technostress Monitoring Systems	Pearson Correlation	1	.594**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
Lecturers’ Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.594**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	360	360

Source: Field Survey (2024) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) *

Pearson Product Moment correlation was run to investigate the relationship between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a positive correlation relationship between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers’ productivity which was statistically significant ($r = .594; N=360; p<0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that “there is no significant relationship between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected and alternate was accepted. The p-value of .000 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between technostress monitoring systems and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with Usoro (2018) found that stress-causing factors such as workload, career progress, facilities and the work setting were significant predictors of academic staff job effectiveness.

Table 2: Pearson’s correlation analysis between technostress strategic planning and lecturers’ productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria.

		Correlations	
Variables		Technostress Strategic Planning	Lecturers’ Productivity
Technostress Strategic Planning	Pearson Correlation	1	.594**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
Lecturers’ Productivity	Pearson Correlation	.594**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	360	360

Source: Field Survey (2024) * Correlation was significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)*

Pearson's Product Moment correlation was run to investigate the relationship between technostress strategic planning and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there was a positive correlation relationship between technostress strategic planning and lecturers' statistically significant productivity ($r = .621$; $N=360$; $p < 0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between technostress strategic planning and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria is rejected and alternate was accepted. The p-value of .000 is less than the 0.05 significance level which indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implied that a statistically, significant relationship existed between technostress strategic planning and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. This finding supported by Onyeizugbe and Ibiam (2021) demonstrates that proper training and support can mitigate technostress, potentially even enhancing productivity.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, technostress is known as technophobia or computer anxiety. The study underscores the need for public university management to develop and implement policies that specifically address technostress. These policies should be integrated into the broader organizational culture to create a supportive and adaptive work environment. Technostress can be properly managed among lecturers in Nigerian public universities through strategic planning and monitoring of lecturers' productivity and the provision of adequate IT facilities. However, the excess workload of lecturers leads to stress and affects their level of productivity in teaching, research and community services as required.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. University management should organize technological training periodically on how to use computer gadgets, relevant software and new hardware for lecturers in the university.
2. The government should sponsor programs like seminars, conferences and symposia to educate and inform academic staff about technostress.
3. University authorities should promote a healthy work-life balance by encouraging breaks and leisure activities to alleviate technostress.
4. University management should provide clear guidelines and instructions on technology use, minimizing uncertainty and anxiety.
5. Public university management should prioritize wellness initiative strategies that would incorporate stress reduction techniques.

REFERENCES

- Abdulganiyu, A. T. (2015). Lecturers' occupational stress and productivity in Kwara State-owned tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts, and Sciences*, 2(4), 55-60.
- Adesina, P. (2021, April 15). Students and stress management. *The Nation*, p. 14.
- Barana, A., Bogino, A., Fioravera, M., & Marchisio, M. (2016). Digital support for university guidance and improvement of study results. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 228, 547-552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.07.084>.
- Dunn, T. J., & Kennedy, M. (2019). Technology enhanced learning in higher education; motivations, engagement and academic achievement. *Computers & Education*, 137, 104-113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.04.004>.
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. New York: Springer.

- Mirzajani, H., Mahmud, R., Fauzi Mohd Ayub, A., & Wong, S. L. (2016). Teachers' acceptance of ICT and its integration in the classroom. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 24(1), 26-40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QAE-06-2014-0025>.
- Narahari, C. L., & Koneru, D. K. (2017). A study of the role of occupational stress in organisations. *International Journal of Engineering Technology, Engineering, Management and Applied Science*, 5, 53-59.
- Shittu, T. O., Ajimuse, M. S., & Idowu, K. O. (2020). Implementation of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions. *FUOYE Journal of Education*, 3(1), 87-92.
- Shittu, T.O., Yekinni, N. L. & Adedapo, O.O. (2022). Academic stress management and lecturers' productivity in public universities in Lagos State, Nigeria. *UJOE*, 5(1), 33-41.
- Tarafdar, M., Cooper, C. L., & Stich, J. F. (2017). The technostress trifecta- techno eustress, techno Distress, and design: Theoretical directions and an agenda for research. *Information Systems Journal*, 29(1), 6-42.
- Usoro, A. A., & Etuk, G. R. (2017). Workload related stress and job effectiveness of university lecturers in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Social Science and Management Studies*, 3(1), 34-41. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.500/2016.3.1/500.1.34.41>
- Wang, B., Deng, K., Wei, W., Zhang, S., Zhou, W., & Yu, S. (2018). Full cycle campus life of college students: A big data case in China. In Du, J. & Kim, C. (Eds.) *Proceedings - 2018 IEEE international conference on big data and smart computing (BigComp)*. Vol. 1 (pp. 507-512). Washington DC, USA: IEEE Computer Society. doi: 10.1109/BigComp.2018.00083.